

TAC Modernization

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NOIRLab’s mission is to “*promote excellence in astronomical research by providing access to information about the Universe from state-of-the-art facilities, surveys, and archives.*” The Time Allocation Committee (TAC) process is an important part of that mission.

The TAC process is a core function of NOIRLab and is used to allocate time on both NOIRLab and privately operated telescopes. We issue calls for standard proposals every six months, and there are opportunities to apply for survey and long-term observing time. The TAC proposal review process operates as part of a larger user support infrastructure.

Although the NOIRLab TAC process is well respected and held up as a standard in the astronomical community, it is evident that both the software infrastructure and processes need to be modernized. We have embarked on a project to upgrade the TAC processes to better support evolving good practices for subjective evaluations, as well as to upgrade the TAC infrastructure to support these changes and improve our user support.

As with other modern subjective evaluation systems, the NOIRLab TAC will be moving to a 2-stage review process. Here we answer some common questions about plans for the new process.

Why is the NOIRLab TAC moving to a 2-stage process?

Several groups have studied proposal acceptance outcomes from their telescope allocation process and concluded that gender bias may be a factor [1], [2]. NOIRLab staff examined proposal acceptance information over 17 semesters from 2008A through 2016A. Total submissions are consistently ~400 proposals per semester. We find that with the exception of 4 semesters (08B, 09B, 11A, 13B), proposals by female principal investigators (PIs) had a consistently lower than expected acceptance rate compared to proposals by male PIs. We recognize that there are many factors that influence TAC decisions about the acceptance (or rejection) of any individual proposal; however, our goal since semester 14A has been to take incremental steps to mitigate the role of unconscious bias in our TAC process.

Why isn’t the NOIRLab TAC adopting the same dual-anonymous process as STScI and NASA?

The NOIRLab TAC team is familiar with the modern good practices for proposal review including lessons learned from the STScI dual-anonymous review process. However, the procedure adopted by STScI is not entirely compatible with some of the mission objectives of our TAC process, including support for thesis datasets and provision of access to researchers at small and underserved institutions. Therefore, we plan to implement our review as a 2-stage process where the first stage includes a review of

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anonymized proposals and the second stage, after a proposal team reveal, allows for ranking adjustments that support NOIRLab mission priorities.

These adjustments include taking into consideration the mission objective mentioned above, i.e., considerations such as thesis proposals and access to researchers at small and underserved institutions. Guidance for panel members (and proposers) will be provided in advance about what makes proposals eligible to be considered for adjustments. Only those proposals with science rankings above or close to the scheduling cutoff will be considered for adjustment.

When will this change to a 2-stage process for the NOIRLab TAC happen?

We anticipate that this 2-stage process will be implemented no earlier than 2022B and at least one semester after the new infrastructure implementation.

Why isn't this change happening sooner?

Our TAC modernization project includes an upgrade of both the TAC process and the TAC infrastructure. The NOIRLab TAC infrastructure upgrade is necessary to implement a system architecture that can support the required procedural changes. Moreover, the current legacy system, which was implemented in the 2000s, is outdated and difficult to maintain, integrates poorly with the TAC database and software frameworks adopted in other parts of NOIRLab, and requires significant manual intervention. Our team plans to have comprehensive documents and instructions available for all stakeholders at the time of rollout of the new procedure.

Will there be other important changes to the proposal process?

Yes. Proposal form fields will no longer support LaTeX formatting, and proposal submissions must be made using the upgraded proposal form. In the future, text sections, such as scientific justification and experimental design, will be accepted as PDF attachments.

Figure 1. The time allocation process includes a number of activities. Among these are proposal acceptance, review panel assembly and ranking, receipt of proposal scheduling and management of notifications. Modernization of the time allocation process will improve the organization of the system workflow, allowing for better automation and new software features that will enable the implementation of current good practice in proposal review. This updated practice will include a dual-anonymous review of proposals in stage one.

References

- [1] Reid, I. N. 2014, *PASP*, 126, 923
- [2] Patat, F. 2016, *arXiv:1610.00920*